

An Expanded Model of Unmatter from Neutrosophic Logic perspective: Towards Matter-Spirit Unity View

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Abstract

In Neutrosophic Logic, a basic assertion is that there are variations of about everything that we can measure; the variations surround three parameters called T, I, F (truth, indeterminacy, falsehood) which can take a range of values. A previous paper in IJNS, 2020 shortly reviews the links among aether and matter creation from the perspective of Neutrosophic Logic. In any case, matter creation process in nature stays a major puzzle for physicists, scientists and other science analysts. To this issue neutrosophic logic offers an answer: "unmatter." This paper examines an extended model of unmatter, to incorporate issue soul solidarity. So, neutrosophic logic may demonstrate helpful in offering goal to long standing clashes.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Logic, Physical Neutrosophy, aether, matter creation, unmatter, unparticle

1.Introduction

In accordance with the quick improvement of new part of basic science, for example neutrosophic logic, here we talk about possible use of NL hypothesis in the field of media transmission. See for ongoing papers: [31-35].

It is known that *matter creation* processes in nature remains a big mystery for physicists, biologists and other science researchers. To this problem neutrosophic logic offers a solution, i.e. *unmatter and unparticle*. See also previous papers on unmatter [21-27].

To put it plainly, neutrosophic logic may demonstrate helpful in offering goal to long standing clashes. See likewise our past papers on this issue. [1-2].

2. Matter creation processes and Grusenick experiment

Physicists all through numerous hundreds of years have bantered over the physical presence of aether medium. Since its origin by Isaac Newton, many accepted that it is required in light of the fact that in any case it is highly unlikely to clarify communication a good ways off in a vacuum space. We need mechanism of connection, of which has been called by different names, for example, quantum vacuum, zero point field, and so forth.

The celebrated Michelson-Morley tests were thought to give invalid outcome to aether speculation, and truly it was the premise of Einstein's STR. In any case, more up to date conversations demonstrated that the proof was fairly equivocal, from MM information itself. Particularly after Dayton Miller examinations of aether float were accounted for, an ever increasing number of information came to help aether speculation, albeit numerous physicists would lean toward another terms, for example, physical vacuum or superfluid vacuum. See [9-13].

In this regards, an experiment which is worthy to mention here is by Grusenick. Actually, his method is quite similar to Michelson-Morley experiment, except that he puts the interferometer *vertically*, which makes him able to detect the vertical aether inflow perpendicularly toward the surface of the Earth. Because only few papers discuss his result, let us give him space to tell in his own words, which can be paraphrased as follows:

"I have perused your information with much intrigue. Numerous individuals state that my development is precisely excessively flimsy, and that gravity impacts my contraption. So I assembled another. A man named Norbert Feist gave me better optical hardware to utilize. The new interferometer is just a steel plate with 189mm width and 8mm thick. The mirrors and the mirror holders are fabricated by Edmund, USA. Their shaft splitter anyway is precisely excessively insecure, so I utilized the one I made myself.

The obstruction design is anticipated on a little bit of paper. During a 180° pivot with the new Interferometer, I can see on normal 1.5 impedance periphery shifts during the night and 2.0 during daytime. With the more established one, which you can find in the YouTube film, there are 11.0 movements around evening time and 11.5 if the trial is performed during daytime. In this way, the two Interferometers (the more seasoned and the more up to date one) show a distinction of 0.5 obstruction periphery shifts among day and night.

I additionally might want to make reference to that a slight variety in the quality of the periphery design development happens during various days of the month. On Thursday 16.10.2009 at 24.00 o'clock, I could see a full 3.0 obstruction periphery shifts per 180° pivot (with the new interferometer). The zero point, where a stop of the example development occurs, is for the two interferometers at a similar position. There are two zero focuses in a 360° turn of the two interferometers when the shaft splitter is situated evenly to the world's surface. To all individuals who state that the main impact on the interferometer is gravity, I have a straightforward inquiry. Why would that be no zero point or stop of the periphery design development when the shaft splitter is in the vertical position? In the pillar splitter's vertical position, the mirrors and the mirror holders are evenly pushed by gravity. In any case, there is no zero point." [19]

According to Paul LaViolette, Grusenick's experiment proves the existence of ether and also his G-ons theory:

"Subquantum Kinetics requires that G etherons (G-ons) reliably diffuse into the Earth, driven by the incline in the Earth's 1/r gravitational conceivable field. The low G-on center inside the Earth, as differentiated and the Earth's space condition, develops considering the way that G-ons are foreseen to be conveyed at an all the more moderate rate in the unbiased issue inside the Earth as differentiated and enveloping space. ... Later

he built up an improved adjustment of the interferometer, showed as follows, and found a total fringe move of 1.5 to 2.0 as the mechanical gathering was turned in the vertical bearing. This value comes closer to that of U.S. investigator Frank Pearce who has played out a type of the Grusenick break down using a 1 inch thick stone square, as opposed to an aluminum board, for mounting the interferometer mirrors and who found a move of just around one half to one outskirts when the mechanical get together was turned in the vertical bearing.”[20]

Alternatively, let us assume that under certain conditions that aether can transform using Bose condensation process to become “*unmatter*”, a transition phase of material, which then it sublimates into matter (solid, gas, liquid). Unmatter can also be considered as “*pre-physical matter*.”

Summarizing our idea, it is depicted in the following block diagram [1]:

Aether → bose condensation → “unmatter” (pre-physical matter) → sublimation → ordinary matter/particle

Diagram 1. How aether becomes ordinary matter

Actually the term “unmatter” can be viewed as a solution from perspective of Neutrosophic Logic. A bit of history of unmatter term may be useful here:

“The word 'Unmatter' was instituted by one of us (F. Smarandache) and distributed in 2004 of every three papers regarding the matter. Unmatter is framed by mixes of issue and antimatter that bound together, or by long-extend blend of issue and antimatter shaping a pitifully coupled stage. The possibility of unparticle was first considered by F. Smarandache in 2004, 2005 and 2006, when he transferred a paper on CERN site and he distributed three papers about what he called 'unmatter', which is another type of issue framed by issue and antimatter that quandary together. Unmatter was presented with regards to 'neutrosophy' (Smarandache, 1995) and 'paradoxism' (Smarandache, 1980), which depend on blends of inverse substances 'An' and 'antiA' along with their neutralities 'neutA' that are in the middle.”¹ See also Christiano & Smarandache [17]. See also F. Smarandache et al.'s papers and books, [21-27].

In any case, in this paper, unmatter is considered as a progress state (pre-physical) from aether to get common particles, see also [1]. Moreover, superfluid model of dark matter has been discussed by some authors [6-7].

3. An expanded model of *unmatter*

In other side, it is known that astronomers find that only 1% of matter in the universe is observed, while 99% is undetected. That is why they call it the Hidden Universe.

¹ <http://fs.unm.edu/unmatter.htm>

Could it be that aether (may be in form of superfluid medium, a ka Mishin phase state) can be intermediate entity in neutrosophic sense?

In this line of thought, it is possible to come up with an expanded model of unmatter, as follows:

Diagram 2. An *expanded model of unmatter*

May be it is because the remaining entities are in the form of consciousness, aether and pre-physical matter. That is what can be called as “*expanded model of unmatter.*”

4. Remark on grid cells, bhutatmas, and consciousness

May be it is possible to come up with a model of how spirit affect matter and vice versa, which reminds us to papers by Ervard Moser et al. on grid cells, space cells etc.

We can add some remark as follows:

“Space cells and grid cells were first discussed by Alfvén (Nobel Prize in Physics) regarding plasma behaviors. I brought it out that these cells have, and evoke, personality traits in all who occupy the given cell, over large spans of time. Which means each star and each cell in the spaces between stars, has a unique personality.

The Russians did a research project that covered most of Asia, and all of Europe, and determined that each cell contains life forms plants animals birds insects fish, and so on, that are unique to that specific cell, and that the people who are native to a given cell have similar personality traits and behaviors unlike the inhabitants of other cells.

The personality of the land of a given cell produces an ambient "personality field" and a unique "magic" that can be learned and used by the inhabitants as a source of benefits which are specific to that cell.

These personality cells are produced by the aether energy-information contents of the plasmas which originate the personality of the given cell. These cell have distinct boundaries and are directly involved with creating life-forms which are perfectly suited to life in the given cell. Some life forms are able to cross over into other cells without undue stresses. Others do not live long when they are removed from their native information-energy habitat.

For life forms which are able to transit and occupy various cells, if the given Being spends a large amount of time in a specific cell, they start to change physically and psychologically in alignment with the qualities of the personality of the land they are spending large amounts of time in.

The Bhutatmas are conveyed by plasmas and "stick to" every material form. Aether clings to matter at all scales, interpenetrating it and forming an atmosphere, similar to the photographs taken by Krasnoholovets of the "atmosphere" of "inertons" which surround electrons. Inertons are much larger than Bhutatmas, however. There are many layers of behaviors related to the smallness of the entities involved which form thresholds of altered physical behaviors, as seen in Pendry structures and other metamaterials.

Air currents, water currents, electrical flows, plasma flows, and all wave forms in all media, regardless of phase state, convey aether and information energy between end points and all along the lines of the flows. Aether circuits are always bi-directional between end-points, while plasma and electrical flows are one-directional. Gravitation and time aether flows also carry information-energy and can alter the given local energetic informational environment fairly rapidly, or over large spans of time.

Marjanovic's model does not cover any of this, as he has no attention for the physics of information-energy, Consciousness, nor studies of the activities of Divinity. Bhutatmas cover all the bases."

Moreover we can add...

"Personality cells are determinant in what kinds of matter are formed, and in where and when they are formed. Stars each have a unique personality, a unique chemistry, and a unique radiation spectrum, exactly because they are formed in different cells with different personalities, which personality cells act as environmental factors during star formation and planet formation.

This is related to the Telluric Intelligence (inhabiting aether rivers) which is endemic to and inherent in each star and each planet. Probably, each Telluric Intelligence is unique, as well as being involved with the unique star and the unique planets associated with the given star.

According to Wal Thornhill and Steven Smith, with whom we agree on this, planets are formed internal to stars by precipitation processes resulting from the creation of atomic elements in the outer-most layers of stars, due to charge separation in stellar plasmas creating enormous gradients in the stellar electric field, thus urging the aether involved with the given star to create new atoms, as put into evidence in the SAFIRE Project. The newly formed atoms tend to precipitate and drift towards the central regions of the given star. Each planet will be unique, but have some traits in common with its parent star.

Uniqueness is partly due to non-local influences being imposed on stellar systems by infinite velocity infinitesimals which carry and convey information to the given stellar system which influence the personality and material composition of the given star. This is a process due to the 5th phase state in Mishin's 5 phase-state aether. (Tesla talks about non-local influences imparting information and various forms of organization to local systems.) This is in addition to the Personality information inherent to the given aether-plasma space-cell, which can modify the local personality over time, and in response to superluminal activities of quantized red-shifts resulting in local variations in the laws of physics in the region, and local variations in the fine structure "constant", leaving leaving the galaxy-core aether-plasmoid in superluminal 3D shells, modifying the physics in the volume of the given out-bound shell."

Hopefully many more approaches can be developed in the direction as mentioned above.

5. Concluding remarks

In this paper, we discussed three possible applications of Neutrosophic Logic in the field of matter creation processes etc. For instance, a redefinition of term "unmatter" is proposed here, where under certain conditions, aether can transform using Bose condensation process to become "*unmatter*", a transition phase of material, which then it sublimates into matter (solid, gas, liquid). Unmatter can also be considered as "pre-physical matter." Moreover, we can extend it further to include consciousness/spirit, which may explain why the 99% of matter in this Universe is undetected. Further researches are recommended in the above directions.

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References

- [1] V. Christianto, R.N. Boyd & F. Smarandache. Three Possible Applications of Neutrosophic Logic in Fundamental and Applied Sciences. *IJNS* Vol. 1 no. 2, pp. 90-95, 2020.
- [2] V. Christianto, F. Smarandache, R.N. Boyd. Electron Model Based Helmholtz’s Electron Vortex & Kolmogorov’s Theory of Turbulence. *Prespacetime J.* Vol. 10 no. 1 (2019) url: <https://prespacetime.com/index.php/pst/article/view/1516>
- [3] V. Christianto & F. Smarandache. One-note-Samba approach to cosmology. *Prespacetime J.*, Vol. 10, no. 6 (2019). <https://prespacetime.com/index.php/pst/article/view/1586/1532>
- [4] <https://www.cosmic-core.org/free/article-99-the-aether-part-2-aether-advocates-experiments/>
- [5] Sinha, Sivaram, Sudharsan. Aether as a superfluid state of particle-antiparticle pairs. *Foundations of Physics*, Vol. 6, No.1 , 1976.
- [6] Sinha. Bose condensation of particle-antiparticle systems. *Pramana – J. Phys.* Vol. 25, 1985.
- [7] Lasha Berezhiani and Justin Houry. Dark Matter Superfluidity and Galactic Dynamics. arXiv:1506.07877 (2015)
- [8] Martin J. Cooper. Vortex Motions in Ideal Bose Superfluid. *JOURNAL OF RESEARCH of the National Bureau of Standards - A. Physics and Chemistry* Val. 73A, No.3, May-June 1969.
- [9] Swenson, Loyd S. "The Michelson–Morley–Miller Experiments before and after 1905," *Journal for the History of Astronomy*. 1 (2): 56–78, 1970.
- [10] Swenson, Loyd S. The Ethereal ether: A History of the Michelson-Morley-Miller Aether-drift Experiments, 1880-1930. The University of Texas – Austin, 2013. url: https://books.google.co.id/books/about/The_Ethereal_Aether.html?id=kQTUAAAAQBAJ&redir_esc=y
- [11] Dayton Miller. The Ether-Drift Experiment and the Determination of the Absolute Motion of the Earth", *Reviews of Modern Physics*, Vol.5(2), p.203-242, July 1933. See also [23a] Dayton Miller, untitled lecture in "Conference on the Michelson-Morley Experiment", *Astrophysical Journal*, LXVIII:341-402, Dec. 1928; also in *Contributions From the Mount Wilson Observatory*, No.373, Carnegie Institution of Washington
- [12] James DeMeo. Dayton J. Miller revisited. In *Should the Laws of Gravitation be Reconsidered?* Hector Monera, Editor, Alleiron, Montreal 2011, 11.285-315. url: <http://www.orgonelab.org/demeopubsPDFs/2011Miller.pdf>
- [13] M. Consoli & A. Pluchino. *Michelson-Morley Experiments: An Enigma for Physics and the History of Science*. World Scientific, 2018. url: <https://www.worldscientific.com/worldscibooks/10.1142/11209>
- [14] James Clark Maxwell. On Physical Line of Forces. [26a] Maxwell, J. C., *A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism*, 3rd edition, Dover, New York, 1954; The Dover edition is an unabridged, slightly altered, republication of the third edition, published by the Clarendon Press in 1891.
- [15] Arthur D. Yaghjian. Reflections on Maxwell’s Treatise. *Progress In Electromagnetics Research*, Vol. 149, 217–249, 2014
- [16] Robert Kowalski. A logic-based approach to conflict resolution. url: <http://www.doc.ic.ac.uk/~rak/papers/conflictresolution.pdf>
- [17] V. Christianto & F. Smarandache. A Review of Seven Applications of Neutrosophic Logic: In Cultural Psychology, Economics Theorizing, Conflict Resolution, Philosophy of Science, etc. *J* 2019, 2(2), 128-137; <https://doi.org/10.3390/j2020010>
- [18] Lydia Patton. Reconsidering Experiments. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*. Vol. 1, No. 2. 2011. Pages 209-226. Official URL: <http://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/660167>

- [19] Martin Grusenick's repetition of the Michelson-Morley interference experiment. url: <http://worldnpa.ning.com/video/extended-michelsonmorley>
- [20] Paul LaViolette. Grusenick experiment proves the existence of the ether and vertical inflow of ether. url: <https://etheric.com/grusenick-experiment-proves-existence-ether/>
- [21] F. Smarandache. Matter, Antimatter, and Unmatter. *Prog. Phys.* 1, 2005. Preprint: EXT-2004-142. url: <http://cdsweb.cern.ch/record/798551>
- [22] F. Smarandache. Verifying Unmatter by Experiments, More Types of Unmatter. *Prog. Phys.* 2, 2005. url: <http://www.ptep-online.com>
- [23] F. Smarandache & D. Rabounski. Unmatter Entities inside Nuclei, Predicted by the Brightsen Nucleon Cluster Model, *Progress in Physics*, 1/2006. url: <http://www.ptep-online.com>
- [24] E. Goldfain & F. Smarandache. On Emergent Physics, "Unparticles" and Exotic "Unmatter" States, *Prog. Phys.* Vol. 4, 10-15, 2008. url: <http://www.ptep-online.com>
- [25] F. Smarandache. Unmatter Plasma Discovered. *Prog. Phys.* Vol. 11, 2015. url: <http://www.ptep-online.com>
- [26] F. Smarandache. *Unmatter Plasma, Relativistic Oblique-Length Contraction Factor, Neutrosophic Diagram and Neutrosophic Degree of Paradoxicity. Articles and Notes.* Brussels: Pons Asbl, 2015. ISBN 978-1-59973-346-3
- [27] F. Smarandache. *Proceedings of the Introduction to Neutrosophic Physics: Unmatter & Unparticle International Conference.* December 2-4, 2011. Ohio: Zip Publ, 2011. ISBN: 9781599731827,
- [28] G. Marjanovic. Pyramids - guardians of primary cosmic vibration of the local densities. *Second International Scientific Conference on Bosnian Valley of the Pyramids*, September 5-10, 2011 Visoko, Bosnia-Herzegovina.
- [29] R.N Boyd. Presentation at *Physics Beyond Relativity Conference*, Prague, Nov. 2019. Link to presentation: <https://science21.cz/conference/?p=901>
- [30] Wallace Thornhill on planet formation: "Wal Thornhill: The Saturn/Earth Connection and Our Place in the Universe | Space News". Link to video presentations: url: <https://youtu.be/6fjcPguafug>, url: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UkPpR8t1qvk>. See also on local brown dwarf star (proto-Saturn): <https://youtu.be/6fjcPguafug?t=420>
- [31] Madeleine Al- Tahan, Some Results on Single Valued Neutrosophic (Weak) Polygroups, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Volume 2 , Issue 1, pp. 38-46, 2020.
- [32] Mohsin Khalid, Young Bae Jun, Mohammad Mohseni Takallo, Neha Andaleeb Khalid, Magnification of MBJ-Neutrosophic Translation on G-Algebra, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science* Volume 2 , Issue 1, pp. 27-37, 2020
- [33] S. A. Edalatpanah, A Direct Model for Triangular Neutrosophic Linear Programming, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Volume 1, Issue 1, pp. 19-28, 2020
- [34] M. Parimala , M. Karthika , Florentin Smarandache , Said Broumi, On $\alpha\omega$ -closed sets and its connectedness in terms of neutrosophic topological spaces, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Volume 2 , Issue 2, pp. 82-88, 2020
- [35] E.O. Adeleke , A.A.A. Agboola , F. Smarandache, Refined Neutrosophic Rings II, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Volume 2 , Issue 2, pp. 89-94, 2020